

TEACHING-LEARNING MODALITY AND RELATED VARIABLES: INPUT TO DEVELOPING SELF-CONFIDENCE AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN ARLING PANLIPUNAN

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ABSTRACT

This study determined students' perceptions on the learner-instructor, learner-content and learner-learner interactions during remote learning activities and its effects on developing self-confidence and academic performance on Araling Panlipunan of ninety Grade 9 junior high school students at the University of Perpetual Help System Dalta – Calamba Campus for SY 2020–2021. Using a validated quantitative questionnaire and a two-tailed test to determine the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient (r), correlation was determined between the three types of interactions, home environment, and school environment with self-confidence and grade point average (GPA). For the interactions, there is a significant correlation between learner-instruction ($r = 0.410$), followed by learner-content ($r = 0.343$), and learner-learner interactions ($r = 0.340$) with self-confidence at 0.01 level. For GPA, there is a significant correlation at 0.05 level for learner-instructor interaction only ($r = 0.237$). Regarding home environment, there is a significant correlation between accessibility ($r = 0.510$), parent reinforcement ($r = 0.448$), and availability of needed materials ($r = 0.275$) with self-confidence at 0.05 level. For the GPA, significant correlation was only found for availability of needed materials ($r = 0.352$) and accessibility ($r = 0.344$) at 0.05 level. On the school environment, there is a significant correlation between emotional support ($r = 0.476$), instructional support ($r = 0.406$), and classroom organization ($r = 0.311$) at 0.05 level. For the GPA, there is a significant correlation for classroom organization ($r = 0.388$) and instructional support ($r = 0.338$) at 0.05 level while there is a significant correlation also for emotional support ($r = 0.270$) At 0.01 level. Based on these results, both self-confidence and GPA has significant relationships on learner-instructor and learner-content interactions, availability of needed materials and accessibility under home environment, and emotional support instructional support, and classroom organization under school environment.

Keywords: teaching-learning modalities, Araling Panlipunan, self-confidence, academic performance